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Research Article

**PREVALENCE OF MEDICAL PROBLEMS AMONG
PATIENTS ATTENDING DENTAL OPD ISLAMIC
INTERNATIONAL DENTAL HOSPITAL**Dr Aroob Pervaiz¹, Dr Khan Zahid Kamal Khan², Dr Kiran Pervez³¹ Lahore Medical and Dental College, Lahore² Rawal Institute of Health Sciences, Islamabad³ Islamic International Dental Hospital and College, Islamabad**Article Received:** December 2019 **Accepted:** January 2020 **Published:** February 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: To explore the frequency of patients suffering from medical disorders who attended for their dental problems in hospital and to explore the relationship of gender with medically conceded dental patients.

Place and Duration: In the Outpatient department Islamic International Dental hospital, Islamabad for one year duration from March 2018 to March 2019.

Material and method: This is a retrospective study. 3087 patients' record were analyzed reporting at the outpatient department studied for the existence of medically compromised disorders. Conditions for deterioration of health were classified in to eight modalities, such as cardiovascular disease, asthma, anemia, liver disease, endocrine disorder, kidney disease, epilepsy and infectious diseases.

Results: 3087 patients; 426 (13.7%) patients had various diseases. The age range of registered patients was 5-80 years, and the average age was 35.04 years (SD ± 15.97 years). 108 (43%) men and 246 (57%) women participated in OPD and the ratio of men to women was 1.36. The most common of these are cardiovascular diseases 387 (90.81%), liver diseases 49 (11.50%), endocrine disorders 188 (44.13%), anemia 77 (18, 07%), kidney diseases 81 (19.01%), infection 43 (10.09%), asthma. 75 (17.62%) and 16 (3.75%) has epilepsy.

Conclusion: Although the incidence of dental diseases is not high, dentists should read the history and conduct a comprehensive clinical investigation prior to dental treatment. We commend appropriate training of dental students in the treatment of patients with medical problems and medical emergencies.

Key words: Dental treatment, medically compromised patient, rescue procedures.

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INTRODUCTION:

As many countries have reported, improved admittance to health care services around the world and enormous scientific progress in latest years have permitted persons to live lengthier with healthier oral hygiene¹⁻³. As a consequence, dental clinics hope to treat older patients with older dentistry because the number of older patients rises the probabilities of treating patients with medical conditions, so the dentist should know their effects⁴⁻⁶.

The aim of this study is to examine the prevalence of patients with dental diseases who want to receive treatment for dental problems and to examine their gender relationship with people with dental problems.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The survey was conducted in the Outpatient department Islamic International Dental hospital, Islamabad for one year duration from March 2018 to March 2019. Sample size 3087 was obtained by including all patients participating in dental OPD.

The hospital standardized history form were used to collect demographic and medical data, asthma, liver disease, kidney disease, infection and epilepsy). Data entered in SPSS 17.0. By descriptive statistics; Data was analyzed. The mean, standard deviation and frequency distribution of individually variable were calculated. The chi-square test was applied to determine the relationship. Less than 0.05 P value was deliberated significant statistically. All diseases are documented individually as a whole, even if they occur together in one patient. If an entry such as age, gender or health condition is not properly entered in the registry, it will be removed from the registry.

RESULTS:

A total of 3,087 patients were enrolled. The age of registered patients is between 5 and 80 years, with an average age of 34.14 years, standard deviation $\pm$ 16.07 years. Of the three thousand and eighty-seven people, 426 (13.79%) presented various diseases. There were 180 (43%) men and 246 (57%) women, the ratio of men to women was 1: 1.36.

Sr.No	Diseases	Total patients	Males total	Females total	M:F ratio
1	Endocrine Disorders	189	74	117	1:1.59
2	Cardio vascular diseases	388	130	236	1:1.62
3	Anemia	80	16	64	1:1.29
4	Asthma	77	33	32	1:3.29
5	Epilepsy	20	11	40	1:1.32
6	Infection	46	20	63	1:1.28
7	Liver diseases	14	8	9	1:0.8
8	Renal	80	9	35	1:1.6

The number of women with medical disabilities was statistically higher than men ($p = 0.000$). In almost all categories of diseases, women had more than men, except for kidney diseases. The most common of these are cardiovascular diseases 387 (90.81%), liver diseases 49 (11.50%), endocrine disorders 188 (44.13%), anemia 77 (18, 07%), kidney diseases 81 (19.01%), infection 43 (10.09%), asthma. 75 (17.62%) and 16 (3.75%) has epilepsy. Most patients with medical problems are in the third and fourth decade.

DISCUSSION:

Due to the aging of the population and new medical and dental techniques, the number of medical complications usually increases during treatment⁸. To avoid these complications, a complete medical history of all these patients should be obtained⁹. The results of this study were similar to the study which showed 12.2% of patients with medical risk associated with Kittipong in 2009. This may be due to the fact that both studies recruited patients in a wide age range.

Smeets et al. The incidence in dental patients was 28.2% in patients with medical conditions. Saengsiravin et al. Diseases in dental patients have been reported to be 55.45%. Smeets et al. Saengsiravin et al study shows that 13.79% of patients with health disorders are against the results of this study. Other 8-9 researchers found that this range was 24.60 to 68.5% higher¹⁰⁻¹¹. This can

happen for many reasons, especially in developing countries such as Pakistan, most patients are not subject to routine medical examinations. As a result, patients receive medically asymptomatic conditions of suffering without realizing that they have health problems¹².

Systemic cardiovascular diseases and endocrine disorders were the most common condition in this study; 90.61% and 44.13%, respectively. Others were still in our study. In this study, more women than men were at medical risk, as demonstrated by a ratio of 1: 1.36 men / women. The results of this study are consistent with the results of the Kittipong ratio (ratio of women to men = 1.5: 1), which shows the superiority of women¹³. This study also increases with age, and the disease is particularly common in women. This trend is second, third. He was observed at the age of four and five, and he finished at the age of six, seven and eight. This may be due to the

exposure of women of childbearing potential to obstetric control, which is why each highlighted disease is documented.

As the number of patients with medical disorders reporting dental treatment increases, this study will help dental surgeons join this part of the patient population. The first step should be to get a correct and meaningful date so you don't lose health. Please note correct registration.

Continuing dental education for dental students and dental treatment of patients at medical risk should be an important part of the dental curriculum, because the literature is about the ability of dentists to deal with these emergencies and medical emergencies¹⁴. Particularly for hypertensive patients, areas should be created raising concerns. Special attention should be given to patients recovering from myocardial infarction¹⁵. More research is needed to get more reliable results. Long-term evaluation of more patients in various dental hospitals is recommended. It is important to include other variables such as; Detailed systemic cardiovascular disease with stages including socioeconomic status, other endocrine disorders and various allergies.

CONCLUSION:

This study claims that medical risk history may play an important role in tailoring dental treatment to the patient's specific health conditions. This is especially important for elderly patients. It should be emphasized that the dentist must be trained to get the correct history and to know the medicines used by patients. The place of treatment should be equipped with all necessary equipment for emergency medical treatment, especially in cardiac emergency.

REFERENCES:

1. Emad, S., Abedi, S., Dehghani, Z. and Ghahramani, Y., 2020. Prevalence of Self-medication with Antibiotics amongst Clients Referred to Outpatient University Dental Clinics in Iranian Population: A Questionnaire-based Study. *Iranian Endodontic Journal*, 15(1), pp.1-5.
2. Jurasic, M.M., Gibson, G., Wehler, C.J., Orner, M.B. and Jones, J.A., 2019. Caries prevalence and associations with medications and medical comorbidities. *Journal of public health dentistry*, 79(1), pp.34-43.
3. Barma, M.D., Leelavathi, L., Indiran, M.A., Rathinavelu, P.K., Doraikanan, S. and Jayashri, P., 2019. Assessment of prevalence and severity of oral impact on daily performances among pediatric outpatients in a dental college. *Drug Invention Today*, 12(6).
4. Iqbal, S.S., Naqvi, S.M.Z.H., Jafry, S.I.A., Hydrie, M.Z.I., Hussain, M. and Adnan, T.A., 2019. Assessment of Depression and Its Associated Factors among Dental Outpatients. *ANNALS OF ABBASI SHAHEED HOSPITAL AND KARACHI MEDICAL & DENTAL COLLEGE*, 24(4), pp.223-230.
5. Noor, A.E., 2019. Pattern of Oro-Dental Problems and Knowledge Regarding Dental Care Practices among the Patients Attending Out Patient Department (OPD) of a Selected Dental College Hospital in Dhaka City. *EC Dental Science*, 18, pp.1604-1619.
6. Seema, N., Ahmed, I., Shireen, F., Rafiq, A., Khan, N.S. and Jadoon, O.K., 2019. FORENSIC ODONTOLOGY AND DENTAL STATUS OF ADULT PATIENTS ATTENDING THE OUT PATIENT DENTAL DEPARTMENT OF A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL. *Journal of Ayub Medical College Abbottabad*, 31(2), pp.233-236.
7. Rizvi, S.Z.R., Naqvi, S.M.Z.H., Jafry, S.I.A. and Abidi, S.M.A., 2019. Dental Anxiety and its Associated Factors Among Patients Visiting Outpatient Department of Different Tertiary Care Dental Hospitals of Karachi. *ANNALS OF ABBASI SHAHEED HOSPITAL AND KARACHI MEDICAL & DENTAL COLLEGE*, 24(3), pp.265-272.
8. Haririan, H., Pachel-Tettinger, D., Kirchner, J., Moritz, A. and Rausch-Fan, X., 2019. The evolution of treatment over 80 years at the outpatient department of the Viennese school of dentistry. *Community dentistry and oral epidemiology*, 47(1), pp.65-70.
9. Wardius, E., Mobini, A., Figueroa, R. and Mehra, P., 2019. Outpatient Anesthesia Morbidity and Mortality Experience Among Massachusetts Oral and Maxillofacial Surgeons. *Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery*, 77(8), pp.1602-1610.
10. Feinstein, J.A., Rodean, J., Hall, M., Douppnik, S.K., Gay, J.C., Markham, J.L., Bettenhausen, J.L., Simmons, J., Garrity, B. and Berry, J.G., 2019. Outpatient Prescription Opioid Use in Pediatric Medicaid Enrollees With Special Health Care Needs. *Pediatrics*, 143(6), p.e20182199.
11. Rivero-Calle, I., Cebey-López, M., Pardo-Seco, J., Yuste, J., Redondo, E., Vargas, D.A., Mascarós, E., Díaz-Maroto, J.L., Linares-Rufo, M., Jimeno, I. and Gil, A., 2019. Lifestyle and comorbid conditions as risk factors for community-acquired pneumonia in outpatient adults (NEUMO-ES-RISK project). *BMJ open respiratory research*, 6(1), p.e000359.
12. Vinodha, C. and Simon, A.K., 2019. AWARENESS OF ORAL HYGIENE AMONG PATIENTS ATTENDING DENTAL OUT PATIENT DEPARTMENT IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN COIMBATORE A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY. *Paripex-Indian Journal Of Research*, 8(4).

13. Sudarssan, S.G. and Wahab, P.U., 2019. Prevalence of Myths and Misconceptions about Dental Extractions among Outpatients of a Private Dental College Hospital. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development*, 10(8), pp.333-338.
14. Li, H.J., Chen, C.Y., Tsai, C.H., Kuo, C.C., Chen, K.H., Chen, K.H. and Li, Y.C., 2019. Utilization and medical costs of outpatient rehabilitation among children with autism spectrum conditions in Taiwan. *BMC health services research*, 19(1), p.354.
15. Sun, M., Sollecito, T.P., Greenberg, M.S., Pinto, A. and Stoopler, E.T., 2019. Analysis of clinical oral medicine practices at the University of Pennsylvania: a 5-year retrospective study. *Oral Surgery, Oral Medicine, Oral Pathology and Oral Radiology*.